

A Dynamic PROMETHEE-Based Lean Manufacturing and Industry 4.0 Implementation Roadmap for Manufacturing SMEs in Emerging Economies

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<p>Abstract</p> <p>This paper presents a decision-support model for generating dynamic, company-specific implementation maps for Lean Manufacturing and Industry 4.0. While the integration of these two paradigms is widely discussed, practical tools that account for a company's current implementation maturity and its own strategic preferences remain scarce, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The proposed model combines a multi-criteria assessment of 18 Lean and Industry 4.0 dimensions with the PROMETHEE II method and GAIA visualization to produce a prioritized implementation sequence. Seven criteria: implementation duration, cost, benefit, risk, administrative constraints, technological capability, and current implementation level, are evaluated by a panel of 18 experts. The current implementation-level criterion links the model to each company's actual state, ensuring that the resulting map is company-specific rather than generic. A sensitivity analysis confirms the marginal stability of the rankings. The model is validated against a sample of 108 SMEs from the manufacturing sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Results show that the ranked sequence can be meaningfully adjusted by changing criterion weights to reflect a company's priorities, demonstrating the model's dynamic character. The paper also provides detailed implementation steps for each dimension, offering practitioners a ready-to-use action framework.</p>	<p>Article history</p> <p>Received: 20.5.2026. Revised: 17.6.2026. Accepted: 23.6.2026.</p> <p>Keywords</p> <p>Lean Manufacturing, Industry 4.0, PROMETHEE, Dynamic Implementation Map, SMEs, Multi-Criteria Decision-Making.</p>
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1 Introduction

Lean Manufacturing and Industry 4.0 have become the dominant paradigms shaping modern manufacturing strategy. Lean, rooted in the Toyota Production System, focuses on eliminating waste, optimizing value streams, and continuously improving people and processes [1]. Industry 4.0, formally introduced at Hannover Messe in 2011 and subsequently elaborated by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research [2], centers on cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things, cloud computing, and data-driven decision-making to create smart factories. Despite apparent philosophical differences – Lean is people – and

process-centered, while Industry 4.0 is technology-driven – the two paradigms are increasingly viewed as complementary [3,4]. A significant body of research confirms positive effects of both Lean and Industry 4.0 on operational and financial performance of manufacturing SMEs [5–9]. Less explored, however, is how companies should sequence their implementation efforts given limited resources, different levels of maturity, and differing strategic priorities. Generic roadmaps exist [10–12], but they are typically static and do not adapt to a specific company's starting position or preferences.

This paper addresses that gap by proposing a dynamic model that (1) measures the current implementation level of 18 Lean and Industry 4.0

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dimensions through a structured survey, (2) applies the PROMETHEE II multi-criteria decision-making method to rank those dimensions for implementation priority, and (3) allows each company to adjust criterion weights according to its own strategic preferences. The resulting output is a personalized, ranked implementation map—dynamic in the sense that it changes as the company's maturity changes or as managerial priorities shift. The model was developed and validated within a study involving 108 manufacturing SMEs from Bosnia and Herzegovina, covering metal and plastics processing sectors. An expert panel of 18 practitioners and academics participated in criterion scoring. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work; Section 3 describes the proposed model; Section 4 presents the results; Section 5 discusses implications; Section 6 concludes.

The principal novelties of this work are threefold. First, unlike existing static roadmaps (e.g., [10–12]), the proposed model dynamically adapts the implementation sequence to each company's real-time maturity profile by incorporating the measured implementation level as a live criterion input (Criterion G). Second, the model integrates Lean and Industry 4.0 dimensions within a single MCDM framework, avoiding the common limitation of treating these paradigms separately. Third, the model is inherently customizable: decision-makers can adjust criterion weights to reflect company-specific priorities without rebuilding the analysis, a capability not offered by any existing roadmap reviewed in Section 2. These characteristics make the model particularly well-suited for manufacturing SMEs in emerging economies, where resources are constrained, and implementation guidance is scarce.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Lean Manufacturing Implementation Assessment

Measuring Lean implementation has attracted sustained research attention. Shah and Ward [13] operationalized Lean through a 10-dimension, 48-item instrument covering supplier feedback, JIT delivery, supplier development, customer

involvement, pull production, continuous flow, setup reduction, statistical process control (SPC), employee involvement, and total productive maintenance (TPM). Malmbrandt and Åhlström [14] developed a 34-item instrument encompassing practices, enablers, and performance indicators. Doolen and Hacker [15] constructed a six-domain framework – production equipment and processes, shop floor management, new product development, supplier management, customer relations, and workforce management – which was validated against 29 practices. These instruments consistently identify that implementation breadth and depth vary significantly across company size and sector [16]. Industry 4.0 Maturity Assessment Maturity models for Industry 4.0 range from the six-dimensional IMPULS model [17] to the nine-dimensional Acatech framework [18] to the PwC self-assessment tool [19]. Tortorella and Fettermann [20] proposed a 10-question survey that covered basic and advanced technologies, grouped into three application areas. A common finding across these models is that SMEs exhibit significantly lower maturity than large firms, with digitization resources and integration being the most lagging dimensions [18,20].

2.2 Implementation Roadmaps and Multi-Criteria Methods

Prior work on implementation roadmaps has employed various MCDM approaches. Ebrahimi, Baboli, and Rother [21] combined AHP with simulation to prioritize Industry 4.0 transformation projects. Kazancoglu and Ozkan-Ozen [22] used Fuzzy DEMATEL to build a competence roadmap for Industry 4.0. Talib et al. [23] applied the Best-Worst Method (BWM) to prioritize 26 JIT implementation practices. Fartash et al. [24] and Ghazinoory et al. [25] both employed PROMETHEE variants for technology roadmapping. A comparative analysis by Wu and Abdul-Nour [26] found PROMETHEE II to provide the most accurate representation of decision-maker preferences among AHP, TOPSIS, ELECTRE III, and PROMETHEE II. Sharma, Kaur, and Bansal [27] likewise concluded that PROMETHEE yields results that are most closely aligned with real-world scenarios. These findings motivated the choice of PROMETHEE II for the present model.

Figure 1 Conceptual model for developing the dynamic implementation map

A gap remains, however: existing roadmaps are typically static (criteria and weights fixed a priori) and do not incorporate a company's current implementation maturity as a dynamic input. The model proposed here fills that gap. t model (Figure 1).

3 Methodology

3.1 Overview of the Model

The dynamic implementation map model consists of three integrated steps, as illustrated in Figure 1:

- 1) Assessment – measuring the current implementation level of each Lean and Industry 4.0 dimension for the target company using a structured survey;
- 2) Multi-criteria analysis – applying PROMETHEE II to rank the 18 dimensions based on seven criteria, with the current implementation level incorporated as one criterion;
- 3) Map generation – producing a prioritized implementation sequence, complemented by detailed project steps for each dimension.

3.2 Alternatives (Implementation Dimensions)

The 18 alternatives (dimensions) evaluated in the model span both Lean Manufacturing and Industry 4.0:

- Lean dimensions (10): Supplier Feedback (POV_DOB), JIT Delivery (JIT), Supplier Development (RAZ_DOB), Customer Involvement (UKLJ_KUP), Pull Production (POV), Continuous Flow (TOK), Setup Reduction (POS), Statistical Process Control (SKP), Employee Involvement (UKLJ_ZAP), and Total Productive Maintenance (CPO).
- Industry 4.0 dimensions (8): People Competencies (KOMP_OSOB), Digitalization and Automation Resources (DIG_AUT), Decentralization (DEC), Data Utilization (POD), Systems (SUS), Core I4.0 Technologies (OT), Advanced I4.0 Technologies (DT), and Integration (INT).

- The Lean dimensions are based on Shah and Ward [13]; the Industry 4.0 dimensions draw on the IMPULS model [17] and Acatech [18]. Each dimension is measured on a five-point Likert scale via a structured questionnaire.

3.3 Criteria

Seven criteria were defined in collaboration with an expert panel of 18 members (10 from academia, 8 from industry) with proven expertise in Lean and Industry 4.0 in the Western Balkans region (Table 1).

Criterion G is what gives the model its dynamic character: as the company improves, its scores change, and the resulting ranking adapts accordingly. Criteria A, B, D, E, and F are minimized; C and G are also conceptually treated as minimized (lower current implementation → higher priority), while Benefit is maximized.

In the initial model, equal weights ($W = 0.143$) were assigned to each of the seven criteria, following expert consensus. Companies may adjust individual weights via the Walking Weights tool in Visual PROMETHEE to reflect their own priorities.

Table 1 Criteria used in the PROMETHEE model.

Criterion	Description
A – Duration	Time required for full or successful implementation of the dimension
B – Cost	All financial costs associated with implementing the dimension
C – Benefit	Measurable desired outcomes from implementing the dimension (maximized)
D – Risk	Undesirable outcomes, including implementation failure or contractual losses
E – Admin. Constraints	Non-technical barriers: management commitment, communication, training
F – Technological Capability	Organizational ability to execute the dimension given available machines, skills, and energy
G – Current Implementation Level	Actual measured implementation score for the target company (from Step 1 survey)

3.3.1 Expert Panel

The 18 experts were selected based on two criteria: (1) a minimum of five years of professional experience in Lean Manufacturing, Industry 4.0, or manufacturing management; and (2) direct familiarity with manufacturing SMEs in the Western Balkans region [32]. The academic members ($n = 10$) were university professors and researchers in industrial engineering and production management with active publication records in Lean and/or Industry 4.0. The industry members ($n = 8$) held roles such as production director, Lean manager, continuous improvement engineer, and plant manager in manufacturing companies from the metal and automotive supply sectors in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia. Average total professional experience was approximately 14 years (range 7–28 years); average direct Lean/4.0 experience was approximately 9 years [32]. Expert judgment validity was ensured through a two-round Delphi-style consensus process: after the first scoring round, inter-rater variance was assessed for each criterion–alternative pair, and items with high variance were discussed in a follow-up session until consensus was reached.

3.4 PROMETHEE Method

PROMETHEE (Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment Evaluations) was developed by Brans in 1982 [28]. For each pair of alternatives a and b , a preference function $P(a,b) \in [0,1]$ is defined, where 0 indicates indifference and 1 strict preference. Six generalized criterion types are available; this model uses the linear preference criterion (Type III) for all criteria.

For the linear preference function (Type III), the indifference threshold $q = 0$ for all criteria, meaning any positive difference between two alternatives triggers a non-zero preference intensity. The strict preference threshold p is set equal to the observed range ($\max - \min$) of expert scores for each criterion [32], so that only an alternative scoring the full spread above another receives a preference intensity of 1. This approach is appropriate when working with bounded expert-scored scales and no prior domain knowledge constrains the thresholds [30,31]. Table 2 presents the exact p and q values for each criterion.

Table 2 PROMETHEE preference function parameters (Type III linear). $q = 0$ for all criteria; p values from [32].

Criterion	Scale	Min/Max	q	p	Threshold rationale
A - Duration	1-5	Min	0	1.5	Expert scores [32]
B - Cost	1-5	Min	0	1.94	Expert scores [32]
C - Benefit	1-5	Max	0	0.67	Expert scores [32]
D - Risk	1-5	Min	0	1.61	Expert scores [32]
E - Admin. Constraints	1-5	Min	0	1.11	Expert scores [32]
F - Tech. Capability	1-5	Min	0	1.72	Expert scores [32]
G - Current Impl. Level	1-5	Min	0	3	Company survey [32]

The multicriteria preference index $\pi(a,b)$ is defined as the weighted sum of pairwise preference functions across all criteria. The positive outranking flow $\varphi^+(a)$ measures how strongly alternative a dominates all others; the negative flow $\varphi^-(a)$ measures how much a is dominated. PROMETHEE II provides a complete ranking using the net flow $\varphi(a) = \varphi^+(a) - \varphi^-(a)$. PROMETHEE I (partial ranking) additionally identifies incomparabilities.

The GAIA (Geometrical Analysis for Interactive Aid) plane provides a two-dimensional visualization of the decision problem using Principal Component Analysis of the covariance matrix of criteria scores, thereby minimizing information loss. Criterion axes in the GAIA plane indicate agreement (similar direction) or conflict (opposing direction) between criteria.

3.5 Sample and Data Collection

The target population comprised small and medium-sized manufacturing enterprises (per EU definition: fewer than 250 employees) registered in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and active in NACE sectors C22, C24, C25, C27, C28, C29, and C30 [32]. From an initial database of 844 firms (Bisnode/Boniteti portal), active companies with manufacturing as the primary activity were retained, yielding a target population of 318. Online questionnaires were distributed to production directors and plant managers; 108 valid responses were received (response rate 33.96%, above the recommended 10% threshold). The sample comprised approximately 60% small and 40% medium enterprises; nearly 80% were from the metal sector, and the remainder from plastics [32].

A separate expert survey was conducted with 18 Lean and Industry 4.0 specialists to score each of the 18 alternatives on criteria A–F (see Section 3.4). Criterion G values were taken directly from the company survey responses [32].

The validation in this study is methodological rather than outcome-based. The 108-company dataset serves two validation purposes: (1) instrument-level validation – the survey scales were assessed for internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha (all CFA-validated dimension scales exceeded $\alpha = 0.70$; range 0.721–0.833, overall $\alpha = 0.812$ [32]) and for construct validity through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA fit indices: CFI = 0.967, TLI = 0.963, SRMR = 0.057, RMSEA = 0.068 [32]); and (2) model-level validation – the PROMETHEE model produces consistent, interpretable, and marginally stable rankings when fed real company data as Criterion G inputs. Longitudinal comparison of predicted versus achieved implementation outcomes is identified as a direction for future research.

4 Results

4.1 Current Implementation Levels

The average Lean implementation level across the sample was 3.54/5.00 [32]. Small enterprises averaged 3.43 and medium enterprises 3.64.

The highest-scoring Lean dimensions were Supplier Feedback and Continuous Flow; the lowest were Statistical Process Control and Supplier Development. The plastics sector (3.79) outperformed the metal sector (3.44) [32].

The average Industry 4.0 implementation level was 2.53/5.00 – substantially lower than Lean [32]. Both small (2.49) and medium (2.58) enterprises ranked Digitalization and Automation Resources and Integration the highest, while Advanced I4.0 Technologies ranked the lowest. The combined average maturity index across both paradigms was 3.04/5.00, indicating that the sample is in an early-to-intermediate stage of adoption [32].

4.2 PROMETHEE Ranking and Implementation Map

Table 3 presents the complete PROMETHEE II net-flow ranking for the analyzed sample [32]. Employee Involvement (UKLJ_ZAP) ranked first with $\phi = 0.3604$, the highest net outranking flow, indicating it dominates all other alternatives under the given criteria and current maturity profile. This result reflects its combination of the highest positive flow ($\phi^+ = 0.3838$) and the lowest negative flow ($\phi^- = 0.0234$) among all alternatives. Supplier Feedback (POV_DOB) ranked second ($\phi = 0.2201$), followed by Setup Reduction (POST, $\phi = 0.1438$) in third place (Table 3).

A clear pattern emerges from the ranking: all nine top-ranked alternatives (ranks 1–9) are Lean Manufacturing dimensions, while Industry 4.0 dimensions occupy ranks 10–18 without exception. This reflects the current maturity gap identified in Section 4.1: with an average I4.0 implementation level of only 2.53/5.00, the model correctly prioritizes Lean foundations before advanced digitalization. The boundary between positive and negative net flows lies between ranks 9 (Pull Production, $\phi = 0.0421$) and 10 (People Competencies, $\phi = -0.0630$), providing a natural demarcation between dimensions that currently outrank the field and those that are outranked.

Table 3 PROMETHEE II complete ranking of 18 Lean and Industry 4.0 implementation dimensions [32]

Rank	Alternative	ϕ^+	ϕ^-	ϕ (net)
1	UKLJ_ZAP – Employee Involvement	0.3838	0.0234	0.3604
2	POV_DOB – Supplier Feedback	0.3425	0.1224	0.2201
3	POST – Setup Reduction	0.2867	0.1429	0.1438
4	JIT_DOB – JIT Delivery	0.2043	0.0698	0.1345
5	RAZ_DOB – Supplier Development	0.2093	0.0967	0.1126
6	SKP – Statistical Process Control	0.1928	0.0812	0.1115
7	CPO – Total Productive Maintenance	0.1854	0.1113	0.0741
8	UKLJ_KUP – Customer Involvement	0.2254	0.1559	0.0695
9	POV – Pull Production	0.1562	0.1141	0.0421
10	KOMP_OSOB – People Competencies	0.1028	0.1658	-0.0630
11	TOK – Continuous Flow	0.1174	0.1990	-0.0816
12	INT – Integration	0.1162	0.2222	-0.1059
13	POD – Data Utilisation	0.1089	0.2270	-0.1181
14	OT – Core I4.0 Technologies	0.0768	0.2246	-0.1477
15	DIG_AUT – Digitalisation & Automation	0.0858	0.2445	-0.1587
16	DEC – Decentralisation	0.0648	0.2350	-0.1702
17	SUS – Systems	0.1155	0.2894	-0.1739
18	DT – Advanced I4.0 Technologies	0.0873	0.3367	-0.2494

At the bottom of the ranking, Advanced I4.0 Technologies (DT) recorded the lowest net flow ($\varphi = -0.2494$), driven by its high implementation cost, long duration, high risk, and the lowest positive outranking flow ($\varphi^+ = 0.0873$). Systems (SUS, $\varphi = -0.1739$) and Decentralization (DEC, $\varphi = -0.1702$) also scored poorly, consistent with the high administrative and technological barriers these dimensions present for resource-constrained SMEs.

The GAIA analysis confirmed that the Benefit criterion (C) and the Current Implementation Level criterion (G) exert the strongest discriminatory influence, as evidenced by the lengths of their vectors in Figure 2 [32]. Criteria oriented in similar directions – Duration (A) and Cost (B) – confirm that shorter and cheaper initiatives tend to be preferred simultaneously, which explains the dominance of Lean dimensions in the upper half of the ranking.

Figure 2 presents the GAIA plane for the analyzed sample [32]. The plane was obtained by reducing the seven-dimensional criterion space to two dimensions via PCA. Key observations: (i) the Benefit (C) and Current Implementation Level (G) vectors point in near-opposite directions, geometrically confirming that dimensions with high expected benefit and simultaneously low current maturity dominate the positive outranking flow; (ii) the Duration (A) and Cost (B) vectors are tightly co-directional, indicating that shorter and less expensive implementations tend to coincide; (iii) the decision axis (red arrow) is oriented toward alternatives corresponding to Employee Involvement, Supplier Feedback, and Setup Reduction; (iv) Advanced I4.0 Technologies and Systems are located in the opposing region, reflecting high cost, long duration, and high current maturity scores.

4.3 Sensitivity Analysis

Weight stability intervals (WSI) were computed for all seven criteria using the Visual Stability Intervals tool in Visual PROMETHEE. Results are reported at stability level 3 (top three alternatives – stronger stability) and level 6 (top six alternatives – broader coverage, one-third of all alternatives [29]) (Table 4).

Figure 2 GAIA plane for the analyzed sample [32]. Criterion vectors: A – Duration, B – Cost, C – Benefit, D – Risk, E – Admin. Constraints, F – Tech. Capability, G – Current Implementation Level. Red arrow = decision axis. Alternatives labeled A1-A18 correspond to the 18 Lean and Industry 4.0 dimensions.

At stability level 6, the WSI ranges are narrow – approximately ± 1 percentage point around the initial equal weight of 14.3% – indicating marginal stability of the top-six ranking.

Table 4. Weight stability intervals at level 3 and level 6 [32].

Criterion	WSI – Level 3 (top 3)	WSI – Level 6 (top 6)
A – Duration	[12.57%, 34.13%]	[13.97%, 14.92%]
B – Cost	[10.38%, 100%]	[13.45%, 14.85%]
C – Benefit	[0.00%, 15.41%]	[14.13%, 14.50%]
D – Risk	[12.07%, 30.86%]	[13.92%, 15.62%]
E – Admin. Constraints	[12.59%, 28.78%]	[14.00%, 15.14%]
F – Tech. Capability	[0.00%, 16.79%]	[13.27%, 14.46%]
G – Current Level	[0.00, 15.97%]	[14.18%, 14.37%]

This means any individual criterion weight fluctuating beyond this corridor will alter the outranking flows sufficiently to reorder at least one of the six top-ranked alternatives. This narrow corridor is a direct consequence of the equal-weight starting configuration ($w_j = 1/7 \approx 14.3\%$ for all j) combined with 18 closely competing alternatives evaluated on 7 criteria.

At stability level 3, the WSI ranges are substantially wider, confirming considerably stronger stability for the top-podium positions (UKLJ_ZAP, POV_DOB, POST). Several results merit particular attention: (i) Criterion B (Cost) shows a WSI of [10.38%, 100%], meaning its weight can be increased to 100% without disturbing the top-3 ranking – a remarkable result indicating that even a purely cost-driven decision-maker would obtain the same top three priorities; (ii) Criteria C (Benefit), F (Tech. Capability), and G (Current Implementation Level) all show lower bounds of 0.00%, meaning these criteria can be entirely removed from the model without altering the top-3 order; (iii) Criterion D (Risk) and A (Duration) show moderate upper bounds of 30.86% and 34.13% respectively, indicating the top-3 remain stable even if these criteria receive more than double the initial weight.

These results carry an important practical message: the recommended top-three implementation priorities – Employee Involvement, Supplier Feedback, and Setup Reduction – are highly robust and should be initiated regardless of how a company weighs its strategic preferences. The sensitivity of ranks 4–6 is moderate (level 6 WSI $\approx \pm 1$ pp), and ranks 7–18 should be revisited whenever managerial priorities shift significantly.

To examine behavior under large weight perturbations, three extreme weighting scenarios were analyzed using the Walking Weights tool [32] (Table 5).

Table 5. Ranking behavior under three extreme weighting scenarios (Walking Weights analysis).

Scenario	Changed weight	Key ranking changes
(a) Speed priority	A = 40%	POST (Setup Reduction) and CPO (TPM) rise; INT (Integration) and SUS (Systems) fall further. Top-3 unchanged.
(b) Cost priority	B = 40%	UKLJ_ZAP, POV_DOB, POST remain top-3. DT and SUS fall to positions 17–18. Mid-range (ranks 7–12) reorders.
(c) Benefit priority	C = 40%	UKLJ_ZAP retains rank 1. TOK (Continuous Flow) and CPO rise into the top 5. I4.0 dimensions remain in the bottom half.

In all three scenarios, the top three alternatives remain in the top five, and the bottom three remain in the bottom five. The most volatile positions are ranks 7–12. The proportional redistribution mechanism of Visual PROMETHEE ensures that when the weight of one criterion increases, the remaining weights decrease proportionally, maintaining $\sum w_j = 1$ at all times [32].

4.4 Dynamic Adjustment of the Map

The model allows real-time adjustment via the Walking Weights feature [32]. For example, increasing the weight of criterion A (Duration) to 25% causes Setup Reduction (POS) and TPM (CPO) to rise in rank, while Integration (INT) falls. Similarly, elevating the weight of criterion B (Cost) raises the priority of lower-cost dimensions such as Employee Involvement and Statistical Process Control.

When a decision-maker adjusts a single criterion weight (e.g., raises Criterion B from 14.3% to 25%), Visual PROMETHEE redistributes the remaining 75% proportionally among the other six criteria. Each remaining criterion i receives: $w_i = w_0 \times (75\% / 85.7\%) \approx 12.5\%$, and the tool renormalizes to $\sum w_j = 1$ at all times [32]. Individual criteria can be fixed before further adjustments, overriding the proportional redistribution.

Furthermore, when a company achieves the maximum score (5/5) on a dimension, that alternative is removed from the decision table, and the model is recomputed, producing an updated map that reflects actual progress [32].

5 Discussion

The results carry several practical implications. First, Lean dimensions – particularly Employee Involvement and Customer Involvement – consistently rank high across companies, suggesting that the human-centered foundations of Lean remain the most accessible and impactful starting points for SMEs, regardless of their Industry 4.0 ambitions. This aligns with findings by Fullerton and Wempe [7] and Sajan et al. [9].

Second, Industry 4.0 dimensions score low in the current maturity assessment (average 2.53/5), yet some – notably People Competencies and Data Utilization – rank comparatively high in the implementation map because their benefit scores are elevated and their current maturity is low. This points to a readiness paradox: companies are aware of the importance of these dimensions but have invested little in them, making them priority targets.

Third, the sensitivity analysis demonstrates that the top-ranked dimensions are marginally stable under equal-weight assumptions, and robust at the extremes of the ranking under large weight perturbations [32]. Dimensions near the boundary (ranks 7–12) are more sensitive and should be revisited whenever priorities change significantly.

A limitation of the study is geographic scope: the sample is restricted to manufacturing SMEs in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, which may limit direct generalisability. The model structure, however, is sector- and country-agnostic and can be applied wherever similar survey data are available. A second limitation is the use of self-reported survey data, which may introduce social desirability bias. Future work should explore objective measurement (e.g., from ERP or MES systems) as a complement or replacement for survey-based criterion G.

Future research could also investigate correlations between Lean and Industry 4.0 dimensions: if implementing TPM positively affects Data Utilization maturity (a plausible synergy), these cross-effects should be incorporated as additional constraints in the PROMETHEE model. Finally, embedding the model in a web-based tool would allow companies to conduct self-assessment and receive a ranked implementation map within a single integrated workflow, as proposed in the doctoral dissertation that underlies this work.

6 Conclusion

This paper proposed and validated a dynamic model for generating personalized Lean Manufacturing and Industry 4.0 implementation maps for manufacturing SMEs in emerging economies, originally developed in [32]. The model integrates a maturity survey, PROMETHEE II multi-criteria ranking, and GAIA visualization. Its defining feature is incorporating the company's current implementation level as a seventh criterion, ensuring the resulting map is company-specific rather than generic. The sensitivity analysis confirmed the marginal stability of the top-six ranking within a ± 1 pp weight corridor and the strong robustness of the top three positions to larger perturbations.

Applied to 108 manufacturing SMEs in Bosnia and Herzegovina [32], the model produced consistent and interpretable rankings. Employee Involvement, Supplier Feedback, and Setup Reduction emerged as the highest-priority dimensions. All nine Lean dimensions ranked above all eight Industry 4.0 dimensions, reflecting the current maturity gap in the sample. The dynamic adjustment capability – through proportional weight redistribution and removal of fully implemented dimensions – ensures the map remains actionable throughout the implementation lifecycle.

Practitioners benefit from a ready-to-use decision tool that translates abstract paradigms into a concrete, prioritized action sequence aligned with their resources and objectives. Researchers are offered a validated MCDM framework that can be

extended to other combinations of paradigms or industrial contexts.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors report there are no competing interests to declare;

Data availability statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author;

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Appendix A: Survey Instrument – Representative Items and Reliability

The following table presents one representative survey item for each of the 18 dimensions, the source from which the item was adapted, and the Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficient from the CFA measurement model [32]. All items were rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = not implemented; 5 = fully implemented).

Cronbach's alpha was computed during the CFA purification process [32]. Dimensions marked "-" did not meet the CFA inclusion threshold ($\alpha < 0.70$) and were excluded from the structural measurement model; their implementation level scores were nonetheless retained as inputs to the PROMETHEE model (Criterion G) based on the theoretical framework [13,17,18]. For the nine CFA-validated dimensions, α ranged from 0.721 to 0.833 (overall scale $\alpha = 0.812$, $N = 34$ items [32]), confirming adequate internal consistency (CFA fit: CFI = 0.967, TLI = 0.963, SRMR = 0.057, RMSEA = 0.068 [32])

Table A1. Representative survey items, sources, and scale reliability [32]. α values from CFA measurement model. — = excluded from SEM model ($\alpha < 0.70$ during CFA purification); scores retained in PROMETHEE model as Criterion G.

Paradigm	Dimension	Representative survey item	α [32]
Lean	Supplier Feedback (POV_DOB)	"Our suppliers visit our factories to understand our production process"	—
	JIT Delivery (JIT)	"Our top suppliers deliver to us on a JIT basis"	—
	Supplier Development (RAZ_DOB)	"We actively work to expand our supplier base"	—
	Customer Involvement (UKLJ_KUP)	"We are in close contact with our customers"	0.750
	Pull Production (POV)	"Production decisions are made only after an order arrives"	—
	Continuous Flow (TOK)	"Production pace is directly linked to customer demand rate"	—
	Setup Reduction (POST)	"Our machines have short setup times"	—
	Statistical Process Control (SKP)	"We use statistical techniques to reduce process variability"	—
	Employee Involvement (UKLJ_ZAP)	"Production workers are key members of problem-solving teams"	0.766
	Total Productive Maintenance (CPO)	"We devote part of each day to planned equipment maintenance"	0.783
Industry 4.0	People Competencies (KOMP_OSOB)	"What skills do employees have in ICT infrastructure for digitalization?"	0.721
	Digitalisation & Automation (DIG_AUT)	"What is the level of comprehensive automation of production equipment?"	0.778
	Decentralization (DEC)	"How do you rate the implementation level of M2M systems?"	—
	Data Utilisation (POD)	"Data are automatically collected and processed in real time"	0.723
	Systems (SUS)	"At what level are ERP systems used in your company?"	0.833
	Core I4.0 Technologies (OSN_I4.0_TEHN)	"At what level are IoT/embedded systems used?"	0.825
	Advanced I4.0 Technologies (DT)	"At what level is AI/cognitive computing used?"	—
	Integration (INT)	"How do you rate the level of vertical integration between departments?"	0.763

Note: The full questionnaire is available from the corresponding author upon request.